

3DPRINT AM35 WIRE ARC ADDITIVELY MANUFACTURED MILLED SPECIMENS UNDER FATIGUE

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Today, wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) can be used to fabricate critical structural steel components. The process enables the fabrication of sophisticated shapes, achieving high levels of material capacity utilisation. Key welding parameters inevitably influence the mechanical resistance of WAAM-fabricated components subjected to static or cyclic loading. This study specifically examines the fatigue behaviour of WAAM carbon steel elements. Firstly, samples are produced by cold metal transfer (CMT) welding process using carbon steel 3Dprint AM 35 (S355) grade, following an optimised welding procedure to minimise induced imperfections. A series of microstructural investigations and mechanical experiments, including static tensile and cyclic fatigue tests, are conducted on milled samples, in both transverse and longitudinal directions. The obtained fatigue test results are then assessed for reliability and validated using Weibull models, commonly employed in survival analysis.

Keywords: Wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM), 3Dprint AM35, Fatigue behaviour, Weibull models

STATE OF THE ART

Introduction

Structurally optimised designs often involve complex geometries, posing challenges to traditional manufacturing methods like forging or casting, which are costly and have limited design flexibility (Buchanan and Gardner [1]). In the last decade, robotic additive manufacturing, particularly gas metal arc welding (GMAW), has gained popularity for its high deposition rate and simplicity (Bhaktavatchalam et al. [2]). Wire-arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) utilises multiple passes to build three-dimensional workpieces, offering precise shaping for efficient material strength utilisation, weight reduction, and environmental impact reduction.

Past research on WAAM

A Web of Science search revealed common keywords related to WAAM research and provided initial insights. Despite WAAM's historical use in metal ornaments since 1925, formal scientific

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investigation began approximately in 2002 (Mu et al. [3]). Exponential expansion in WAAM research commenced in 2013, with 218 research papers by mid-2023 and an anticipated 600 by the year-end. Publications predominantly focused on microstructure, mechanical properties (encompassing fatigue, thermal stress, and welding defects' influence), and high-cycle fatigue. Noteworthy studies include the characterisation of pore formation and distribution post-welding, surface roughness, and the initiation and progression of cracks in aluminium, titanium, and stainless steel alloys (Zhong et al. [4], Gordon et al. [5] and Hönnige et al. [6]).

The construction sector maintains a robust interest in conventionally low to moderately alloyed carbon steel grades, known for good weldability, machineability, and suitable mechanical strength for WAAM applications (Kawalkar et al. [7]). Ongoing WAAM investigations predominantly concentrate on low-alloyed carbon steel ER70S6. Studies explore uniaxial, multi-axial, and bending fatigue resistance (Ermakova et al. [8]), the correlation between microstructure and mechanical behaviour (Ron et al. [9]), fatigue crack growth, and investigation of failure mechanisms and modes of fracture (Bhattacharya et al. [10]). Significantly, there is a scarcity of studies on WAAM components manufactured from non-alloyed carbon steel grade S355 (3Dprint AM35). Given its potential applications, acquiring reliable experimental data on cyclic loading behaviour, especially for offshore wind turbines, is crucial.

Project objectives and content of the paper

The project that this paper summarises investigated the mechanical behaviour of WAAM-produced carbon steel 3Dprint AM 35 (S355) and explored their microstructure and mechanical characteristics. The project involved assessing static tensile strength and experimentally characterising fatigue behaviour under diverse stress ranges, conducting tests in both transverse and longitudinal directions (TD and LD). The next section of this paper details the project's experimental program, detailing process parameters, component production, and specimen preparation. It then presents microstructure measurements, static tensile tests, and cyclic fatigue tests. The latter results are then juxtaposed with the current detail categories proposed in the Eurocode 3 [12] and IIW provisions (Hobbacher [11]). Last, we validate the reliability of proposed detail categories for WAAM components draw conclusions on the applicability of WAAM components in fatigue-prone applications using low-alloyed carbon steel grades.

SPECIMEN MANUFACTURE

Welding procedure and process parameters

The study utilised the Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) process with a Fronius TPS600i power source and a KUKA robot (6-axis KR16 R2010) to produce the specimens. Welding was performed using a 3Dprint AM35 solid wire (1.2mm diameter) on an unalloyed carbon steel S355 substrate. WAAM deposition parameters involved an average welding power of 2500W, deposition speed of 0.6 m/min, wire feed speed of 3.6 m/min, contact tip to work distance of 12 mm, M20ArC8 shielding gas. The specimens, measuring 1052mm×27mm×503mm, consisted of 200 layers with a nominal thickness of 2.515mm each, see FIGURE 1. The welding trajectory followed a zig-zag pattern, alternating start and end points, with a 3.5mm stepover and 5 s interpass time between adjacent layers. This approach aimed to reduce residual stress, enhance dimensional accuracy, and prevent overheating for improved welding quality and fusion.

FIGURE 1 Photograph of a sample during and after the CMT process.

Dimensions of samples

Two large specimens were welded, resulting in a total of 32 dog-bone coupons for fatigue tests and 6 for static tensile tests, as seen in FIGURE 2, (a) and (b). The specimens were waterjet cut with a 4 mm finishing allowance, as shown in FIGURE 2 (c). "Specimen 1" underwent fatigue testing with the label "AW" denoting as-welded tests, indicating no post-weld heat treatment. "Specimen 2" in FIGURE 2 (b) provided dog-bone coupons for tensile tests and additional fatigue specimens. Tolerances for parallel lengths adhered to EN ISO 6892-1 for tensile testing and ASTM standard E466-21 for fatigue testing. All walls were milled to an average surface roughness of $0.4 \mu\text{m Ra}$.

FIGURE 2 Schematic of the extracted samples: (a) for fatigue testing; (b) for tensile and further fatigue testing; (c) coupon dimensions (left for fatigue and right for tensile testing).

EXPERIMENTS

Microstructural investigation

Destructive examinations evaluated microstructure mass balance on specimens, cut, polished, and chemically etched with 2% Nital. The Hirox KH-8700 optical microscope characterised microstructure, grain sizes, and anomalies. Following ASTM E562, 30 images per zone were captured to measure ferrite content using Image J software. The investigations revealed two zones between welding passes: (i) zone 1 with fine ferrite and cementite, and (ii) zone 2 with dendritic ferrite and pearlite. Ferrite distribution showed lower percentage and less scatter in zone 1 than zone 2. Findings align with those in unwelded carbon steel specimens, displaying analogous trends in

microstructural characteristics (Callister and Rethwisch [13]). Uncontrolled carbon additions or rapid cooling can reduce ductile pearlite and promote brittle cementite formation (Islam and Rached [14]). Both fine ferrite and dendritic ferrite exhibit finer grain structures, positively impacting fatigue behaviour by extending the crack initiation phase.

Static tensile tests

Static tensile tests were conducted on dog-bone coupons (three with a 12 mm thickness each) in both the rolling direction (RD) and transverse direction (TD). An Instron 1500 HDX series static tensile-compression bench was used following a displacement-controlled loading protocol according to EN ISO 6892-1. A strain rate of 0.00007 s^{-1} was employed in the elastic range, increased to 0.00025 s^{-1} until failure. Digital image correlation (DIC) measured the displacement field, and virtual fields method (VFM) processed the data following Kramer and Scherzinger [15]. Two cameras (Manta G-895, 8.95 Megapixel resolution) were positioned 300 mm away at a 45° angle. The speckle pattern on the specimens did not exceed 0.4 by 0.4 mm, based on camera properties and the test setup. MatchID software was used for post-processing the data.

The engineering stress-strain relation [13] was derived based on the average measured strain field along the specimen's parallel length using a region of interest (ROI) shown in FIGURE 3. To capture true strain and study material behaviour at fracture and extreme plastic deformation, a smaller ROI was used. DIC post-processing parameters included a strain window (SW) of 15 pixels, step size (ST) of 10 pixels, and subset size (SS) of 25 pixels. This yielded in a Virtual Strain Gauge (VSG) size of 165 pixels corresponding to a physical size of 10 mm. These parameters were selected through sensitivity analysis to ensure insensitivity of the maximum principal stress component to the VSG size without exceeding the physical strain gauge size, preventing unnecessary averaging and maintaining accuracy. A representation of a typical strain field for one of the tests in the RD is shown in FIGURE 3. In addition to DIC, 3 strain gauges were attached around each specimen and provided measurements in close agreement with those obtained through DIC.

The elasticity modulus – E , upper yield strength – f_y , ultimate strength – f_u , ultimate strain – ε_u and total strain at failure – ε_t were calculated according to EN ISO 6892-1. The average values and corresponding standard deviation ($Stdv$), TABLE 1, are in good agreement with the nominal values provided in EN 10025-3.

TABLE 1 Average static tensile test results of the as-welded specimens for LD and TD (based on DIC results).

	E [GPa]	$Stdv E$ [2σ]	f_y [MPa]	$Stdv f_y$ [σ]	f_u [MPa]	ε_u [%]	ε_t [%]
As-welded LD	206	2.39	359	7.31	445	18.0	29
As-welded TD	209	1.83	362	3.33	448	17.0	26

FIGURE 3 Tensile coupon test: Typical measured strain field by Digital Image Correlation and ROI's.

Cyclic fatigue tests

TABLE 2 Fatigue strength of additively manufactured specimens studied in this paper.

Material	Number of tests – n	$FAT_{k,NSM} / FAT_{m,NSM} / FAT_{u,NSM}$ ($m = 5$) [MPa]	$FAT_{k,NSM} / FAT_{m,NSM} / FAT_{u,NSM}$ ($m_{var} > 5$) [MPa]
As-welded LD	25	219.78 / 265.85 / 321.57 (CoV=0.010)	335.02 / 342.54 / 350.24 (CoV=0.002) ($m_{var} = 50$)
As-welded TD	18	217.18 / 255.81 / 301.32 (CoV=0.009)	314.75 / 325.66 / 336.95 (CoV=0.003) ($m_{var} = 22$)
As-welded LD&TD	43	220.45 / 259.53 / 305.54 (CoV=0.010)	289.18 / 309.32 / 330.87 (CoV=0.005) ($m_{var} = 12$)

A total of 32 cyclic fatigue tests were conducted using an Instron 8802 series servo-hydraulic testing actuator, to establish the Wöhler curve for additively manufactured specimens. The fatigue resistance assessed based on the nominal stress method (NSM) was compared to the IIW guidelines recommendations [11], i.e., FAT160 with a fixed slope of $m = 5$. This detail category is chosen based on the assumption that milled specimens behave similarly to unwelded base plates produced conventionally, making $m = 5$ more suitable than $m = 3$, as suggested in fatigue design guidelines [11], [12].

Utilising linear regression analysis with a fixed slope, the characteristic fatigue resistance FAT_k , i.e., the stress range at 2×10^6 cycles, was calculated. FAT_k corresponds to a 95% survival probability, while the mean fatigue resistance (FAT_m) corresponds to a 50% survival probability. A two-sided confidence of 75% was applied while calculating the characteristic values. First, a fixed slope of $m = 5$ was considered, then a best-fitting slope was obtained to minimise the standard

deviation among the assessed data population ($\log C$ values as per [11]). TABLE 2 provides an overview of the results.

The regression analysis was carried out in accordance with the IIW recommendations using Equations (1) to (3).

$$\log N = \log C - m \cdot \log \Delta \sigma \tag{1}$$

$$X_k = X_m \pm k \cdot Stdv \tag{2}$$

$$k = 1.645 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \right) \tag{3}$$

where C represents the constant that denotes either the fatigue strength coefficient or the intercept of the Wöhler curve. X_m stands for the mean of $\log C$ values, while X_k represents the characteristic value associated with X_m . $Stdv$ denotes the standard deviation of $\log C$ values, and k signifies the factor representing the number of standard deviations from the mean. For instance, selecting k as 2 accounts for two standard deviations from the mean, covering approximately 95% of the data. The IIW guidelines propose a value for k as a function of n , the number of test samples, offering greater flexibility in determining the level of certainty or risk tolerance. Moreover, test results with a fatigue life $N \geq 5 \times 10^6$, surpassing the constant amplitude fatigue limit, fall within the ultra-high cycle fatigue range and were excluded from the statistical analysis as per references [11] and [12].

FIGURE 4 Fatigue test results of combined as-welded LD and TD specimens against Eq. (1) with $m = 5$ versus m_{var} .

The fatigue performance of longitudinal (LD) and transverse direction (TD) specimens is similar due to the beneficial bonding created by the zig-zag trajectory (Ferreira et al. [16]). Considering isotropic behaviour, results for LD and TD are combined in FIGURE 4, depicting fatigue lives for all tests. For stress ranges $\Delta \sigma$ between 340 MPa and 355 MPa, there was notable variability in the number of cycles, with runout tests below 340 MPa and low-cycle fatigue observed above 355 MPa (see FIGURE 4). All tests were carried out with a stress ratio (R) equals 0.1. All tests, conducted

with a stress ratio (R) of 0.1, revealed that using a fixed slope of $m = 5$ positions the examined additively manufactured samples significantly above the codified fatigue class in Eurocode 3 and IIW guidelines [11], [12]. The experimental lower bound is $FAT_k = 220.45$ surpassing the specified fatigue class of 160 MPa, TABLE 2. It is evident that employing a higher slope in practice would align better with results having lower scatter, see TABLE 2. In such a scenario, the highest fatigue category can be confidently applied.

RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT

Two-parameter Weibull distribution

Weibull models, widely employed in survival analysis and reliability studies, assess the probability of failure based on a continuous variable, "strength" (represented as N, denoting fatigue lives in this context). The scale and shape parameters are determined through a mathematical fitting process. This chapter analyses Wöhler curves from Section 3 using the traditional two-parameter Weibull distribution (Weibull [17]). Various researchers, including Barbosa et al. [18], Pedrosa et al. [19], and Karabulut et al. [20], have applied this traditional model to evaluate reliability levels of proposed fatigue detail categories. Equation (4) presents the cumulative probability function, utilising a two-parameter model introduced by [17] for analytical estimation techniques. Equation (5), based on Bernard's median rank method proposed by Fothergill [21], provides the probability of failure at a specific time, referring to the number of cycles in this instance, and is employed to derive the experimental Weibull curve.

$$P(N) = 1 - e^{-\left[\frac{N}{\alpha_w}\right]^{\beta_w}} \quad (4)$$

$$P(N_i) = \frac{i - 0.3}{n + 0.4} \quad (5)$$

where N represents the number of cycles until failure, it's normalized as the ratio of $\log N$ (mean curve) acquired in Equation (1) to the $\log N$ obtained experimentally. α_w stands for the scale parameter, and β_w represents the shape parameter, both fitted against the experimental population. The shape parameter directly impacts the form of the distribution, while the scale parameter α_w determines the extent of the distribution function's spread.

To estimate the scale and shape parameters α_w and β_w , three techniques were applied, following the methodology proposed in (Goglio and Rosetto [22]). Equation (6) outlines the Maximum Likelihood Method (MLM), where log-likelihood function is maximised to determine α_w and β_w . This involves using the Newton-Rapson technique, initiating with initial parameter guesses and iteratively updating based on the derivative of the log-likelihood function until convergence.

$$\begin{aligned} &L(\alpha_w, \beta_w | N) \\ &= \left(\frac{\beta_w}{\alpha_w \beta_w}\right)^n \prod_{i=1}^n \left\{ N_i [\beta_w - 1] \exp \left[- \left(\frac{N_i}{\alpha_w} \right)^{\beta_w} \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where, L is the likelihood function and n stands for the sample size.

Additionally, equations (7) and (8) refer to the Linear Least Squares Method (LLSM) [18].

$$\alpha_w = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n X_i)^2} \tag{7}$$

$$\beta_w = \exp\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i - \alpha_w \sum_{i=1}^n X_i}{n \alpha_w}\right) \tag{8}$$

where X_i and Y_i denote two linear parameters that are related to N_i [19]. The Weibull parameters can then be estimated through linear regression, as detailed in [18].

Last, equations (9) and (10) refer to the Weighted Linear Least Squares Method (WLLSM) (Zhang et al. [23]), which estimates α_w and β_w using weighted linear regression.

$$\alpha_w = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i Y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i \sum_{i=1}^n w_i Y_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i)^2} \tag{9}$$

$$\beta_w = \exp\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i Y_i - \alpha_w \sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\alpha_w \sum_{i=1}^n w_i}\right) \tag{10}$$

$$w_i = 0.076 + 3.610P(N_i) - 6.867P(N_i)^2 + 13.54P(N_i)^3 - 9.231P(N_i)^4 \tag{11}$$

where w_i represents the weighting of X_i and Y_i values, contingent upon the estimated values of the cumulative probability function $P(N_i)$, thereby influencing the model's dependence on observations. These weights are determined through a polynomial fitting process that correlates w_i with $P(N_i)$ as delineated in Equation (11); refer to [23] for further elucidation.

To assess the concordance between the Weibull distribution and data acquired experimentally, a goodness to fit analysis was conducted according to equation (12), i.e. the χ^2 test. The χ^2 test assesses differences in frequencies within specified intervals between empirical and theoretical (expected) data distributions. For the goodness to fit tests, lower values indicate a better fit between the observed data and the Weibull distribution. Additionally, utilising the theoretically derived Weibull distribution function allows the computation of a fatigue category corresponding to a given reliability level (RL), commonly set at 90%, as observed in literature [19], [24].

$$\chi^2 = \frac{\left(P(N_i)_{emp.} - P(N_i)\right)^2}{P(N_i)} \tag{12}$$

The two-parameter Weibull distribution function was fitted against the results from the tests presented in Chapter 3. The estimated parameters of the Weibull distribution, including α_w and β_w , along with their corresponding evaluated detail categories, are detailed in

TABLE 3.

TABLE 3 Estimated Weibull parameters, goodness-of-fit and fatigue strengths for the studied additively manufactured specimens in this paper.

Estimation method		LD&TD		
		MLM	LLSM	WLLSM
α_w		2.63	2.81	2.38
β_w		1.22	1.22	1.20
Goodness-of-fit	χ^2	0.21	0.20	0.34

Fatigue strength [MPa]	RL 90 %	227.64	229.90	222.78
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Discussion on the reliability assessment

All data in

TABLE 3 show β_w values exceeding 1.0, signifying that all samples experienced fatigue failure without premature or other types of failure. χ^2 tests help differentiate between estimation methods, with the Linear Least Squares Method (LLSM) consistently outperforming other methods, see

TABLE 3. This finding aligns with prior studies emphasising the preference for χ^2 tests in evaluating the fit of fatigue test results to the Weibull distribution [20]. The previously determined fatigue class denoted as FAT_k 220.45 MPa in TABLE 2 is further validated as a reliability level of 0.90 corresponds to a fatigue class of 229.90 MPa. Hence, it is reliable to recommend using a fatigue class of 220 MPa with a fixed slope of $m = 5$ for the studied WAAM AM35 component.

Ultimately, considering the higher best fitting slopes examined previously, the same analysis was conducted again. The Weibull parameters were re-calculated considering the LLSM and goodness of fit was re-assessed using the χ^2 test. A higher best fitting slope ($m_{var} > 5$) results in a better fit, i.e. lower χ^2 test results equal to 0.16, for the examined WAAM details. When the best fitting slope $m_{var} = 12$ is considered, the obtained reliable fatigue class increases to 294.23 MPa. For more details regarding the reliability assessment and for the comparison with a larger database collated from the literature, one can refer to Karabulut et al. [25].

CONCLUSIONS

This study investigates the fatigue performance of wire arc additively manufactured (WAAM) components using unalloyed S355 steel, specifically AM35 3D-Print. Experimental results include microstructure analysis, tensile tests, and fatigue tests. As-welded samples exhibit excellent fatigue lives, surpassing the highest fatigue class in design standards like Eurocodes or IIW guidelines. This is attributed to fine grains, low porosity, and low tensile residual stress. The zig-zag trajectory minimises microstructural variations and residual stresses, leading to consistent mechanical characteristics, better layer bonding, and accurate final shapes with less distortion [16]. Fatigue detail categories (at 2×10^6 cycles) are computed, and Weibull distribution confirms their reliability levels (90%). The current slope of $m = 5$ in design guidelines appears inadequate for additively manufactured plates; considering a best fitting slope of $m = 12$, the reliable detail category becomes 294.23 MPa. For WAAM structures with S355 carbon steel grades in fatigue-prone applications, we recommend basing fatigue designs on these findings (applicable to milled surfaces).

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REFERENCES

- (1) Buchanan, C., and Gardner, L., *Eng Struct*, Vol. 180, No. 332, 2019, pp. 332-348.

- (2) Bhakthavatchalam, U., Ganeshmurthy, K., Jaisooriyan, A., *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, Vol. 1, 2018.
- (3) Mu, H., He, F., Yuan, L., Commins, P., Wang, H., Pan, Z., *J Manuf Syst*, Vol. 67, 2023, pp.174-189.
- (4) Zhong, H., Qi, B., Cong, B., Qi, Z., Sun, H., *Chinese Journal of Mechanical Engineering (English Edition)*, Vol. 32, No. 92, 2019.
- (5) Gordon, J. V., Haden, C. V., Nied, H. F., Vinci, R. P., Harlow, D. G., *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, Vol. 724, 2018, pp. 431-438.
- (6) Hönnige, J. R., Colegrove, P., Williams, S., *Procedia Eng*, Vol. 216, 2017, pp. 8-17.
- (7) Kawalkar, R., Dubey, H. K., Lokhande, S. P., *Mater Today Proc*, Vol. 50, 2022, pp. 1983-1990.
- (8) Ermakova, A., Razavi, N., Berto, F., Mehmanparast, A., *Int J Fatigue*, Vol. 166, 2023.
- (9) Ron, T., Levy, G. K., Dolev, O., Leon, A., Shirizly, A., Aghion, E., *Metals 2020*, Vol. 10(1), No. 98, 2020.
- (10) Bhattacharya, A., Paul, S. K., Sharma, A., *Eng Fail Anal*, Vol. 150, No. 107347, 2023.
- (11) Hobbacher, A. F., *Recommendations for Fatigue Design of Welded Joints and Components*, International Institute Of Welding (IIW), Springer International Publishing, 2016.
- (12) EN 1993-1-9, *European Committee for Standardization, 2005. EN 1993-1-9, Eurocode 9: Design of Steel Structures - Part 1-9: Fatigue.*, CEN, Brussels., 2005.
- (13) Callister Jr, W. D., and Rethwisch, D. G., *Materials Science and Engineering an Introduction*, Wiley, 2007.
- (14) Islam, T., and Rashed, H. M. M. A., *Reference Module in Materials Science and Materials Engineering*, 2019.
- (15) Kramer, S. L. B., and Scherzinger, W. M., *Implementation and Evaluation of the Virtual Fields Method: Determining Constitutive Model Parameters From Full-Field Deformation Data* Sandia National Laboratories, 2014.
- (16) Ferreira, R. P., Vilarinho, L. O., Scotti, A., *Welding in the World*, Vol. 66, 2022, pp. 455-470.
- (17) Weibull, W., *J Appl Mech*, Vol. 18, 1951, pp. 293-297.
- (18) Barbosa, J. F., *Performance of Fatigue Life Models Based on Reliable Estimators and an Artificial Neural Network for Materials*, Universidade Federal Do Rio Grande Do Norte Centro De Tecnologia, 2019.
- (19) Pedrosa, B., Correia, J. A. F. O., Rebelo, C. A. S., Veljkovic, M., *ASCE ASME J Risk Uncertain Eng Syst A Civ Eng*, Vol. 6, No. 3, 2020.
- (20) Karabulut, B., Ferraz, G., Rossi, B., *J Constr Steel Res*, Vol. 211, No. 108154, 2023.
- (21) Fothergill, J. C., *IEEE Transactions on Electrical Insulation*, Vol. 25, No. 3, 1990, pp. 489-492.
- (22) Goglio, L., and Rossetto, M., *Eng Fract Mech*, Vol. 71, No. 4-6, 2004, pp. 725-736.
- (23) Zhang, L. F., Xie, M., Tang, L. C., *Springer Series in Reliability Engineering*, Vol. 18, 2008, pp. 57-84.
- (24) Bai, Y., Jin, W.-L., *Marine Structural Design* 2016, 645.

(25) Karabulut, B., Ruan, X., Mac Donald, S., Dobric, J., Rossi, B., *Int J Fatigue* 2024, 108317.